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Annotation. The century of digital technology has brought information presentation to a new, higher level of quality. Thanks to computers and presentation software, anyone can compile a report covering any topic in an understandable format. Only the right knowledge and the right software are needed for a successful presentation.

Over recent years, relationships between reading, writing and technology have played out in diverse and multiple ways. For some, work has focused on using new technologies to support the development of particular literacy skills whilst others have responded to new technologies by exploring the possibilities for new literacy practices. All this has implications for how we see reading and writing and consequently for literacy pedagogies. The collection of articles in this virtual issue demonstrates this diversity. Some provide precise insights into the impact of particular approaches or tools; others raise questions about possible continuities and discontinuities between literacy as practised and understood in educational establishments and in spaces outside academia. Reports of research which focuses on spaces and practices beyond educational contexts help us see and understand uses of new technologies for meaning making in informal contexts, where learning often happens in less structured ways than in schools, for example. Graham's work explores how teachers' school-based uses of digital technologies are influenced by their biographies of digital learning. She identifies different types of learner, reflecting on how the varying contexts of these teachers' digital learning experiences have impacted on their practices in the classroom. Her reflections that teachers need time to consolidate their learning and to feel relaxed about using digital technologies would perhaps have benefited the teachers that Honan describes in her research. Honan finds that despite teachers' intentions there often remain seemingly insurmountable barriers to their employment of digital technologies in the classroom. Further she argues that often even where the technologies are used they are not used in ways which make the best use of the affordances of the technologies. Like Graham, she finds a link between those teachers who do not use technologies in their everyday lives, with this group encountering most barriers for embedding digital tools into their classroom practices. She argues that teachers need the space to develop their ideas about the relationship between new technologies and literacy learning; to see the benefits that technologies can bring; and how they represent a qualitative difference to the concept of literacy and 'being literate'.

In a report of a study following a group of learners and a group of pre-service teachers working in a virtual environment, Gomez, Schieble, Curwood and Hassett argue that there are many advantages to be gained in terms of literacy development. They suggest students' critical literacy develops when they work in collaborative online contexts - and that this instigates a 'distributed cognition' where individual achievement is less important than distributed cognition. They show how in a virtual space where collaboration is key, that learners are able to develop the skills to become more critical. Kendall's work gives us, as literacy educators and researchers, insights into the reading lives of young adults between the ages of 16 and 19. In revealing to us the reading habits and interests of these young people, whose tastes in reading are often considered 'low-brow' or their choice of texts as 'throw-away'. Kendall asks us to reflect on our own positions and that we critically reflect on our values as educators. In the same vein, Dowdall explores the 'dissonance between the digitally created words of

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

home and school'. Dowdall traces the home-based activities of a young girl, Clare, using an online social networking site and compares her text creation of these home based texts in the site, to texts Clare produces for school. While there are differences between the ways Clare's home and school texts are structured and written, there are nevertheless continuities across them. Dowdall concludes that whilst we might see many differences between the texts, that we as readers might be placing undue significance to these differences and that close reading shows similarities across the texts. Here Dowdall's work echoes that of Kendall, that we as educators and researchers, might suppose there are more differences between home and school cultures, and that we need to reflect on our selves as readers more closely.

More psychologically orientated work around technology and literacy has centred on the need to demonstrate the educational impact and efficacy of computer-mediated approaches to reading remediation. To examine this issue, studies have moved towards randomized control trial formats to ensure that the results presented are as unambiguous as possible. The results from such work to date have yielded intriguing results. For example, Wild conducted a direct comparison of computer-based and paper-based phonological awareness exercises. The results showed that the use of the computer as a presentation format did appear to impact on the children's attainment, albeit to a modest extent. However, they also showed that this benefit was greatest for the girls in the sample. Computers have been used to examine claims about the efficacy of analytic vs synthetic phonics approaches. The advantage here is that computers, it can be argued, offer a more standardized format for the delivery of such content, thereby offering a more stringent examination of such claims.

Research studies have emphasized the importance of learners' literacy achievements vital later academic success (Justice, 2007; Nutbrown, Hannon, & Morgan, 2005). Teaching reading and writing should be an exciting and meaningful experience that captures learners' interests and enriches their experiences. Fisher (2000) stated that because early literacy is so important, early childhood educators should discover the best ways to help children achieve a high level of literacy. These practices include creating a print-rich classroom environment through the use of genuine literature, establishing literacy centers, increasing opportunities for social collaboration among children, and providing extensive professional development for teachers. In addition, researchers have emphasized that technology, particularly computer-related technology, plays a fundamental role in improving teachers' instructional practices and, therefore, developing children's literacy skills. For example, Dodge et al. (2003) indicated that computer technology has a number of

valuable advantages in terms of supporting learners reading and writing skills:

- (1) expanding learners' vocabulary and language development by introducing them to software that associates vocabulary with pictures, written words, and spoken words;
- (2) helping learners develop phonological awareness with interactive software that plays with language;
- (3) increasing learner's understanding of books by exposing them to electronic books;
- (4) enhancing learner's knowledge of print by recording their responses on a word processing/reading program;
- (5) offering learners practice in learning about writing essays
- (6) developing learners' enjoyment of literacy by letting them explore electronic storybooks.

Computers enhance and develop young learner's emergent reading and writing skills. This can be achieved when children are actively engaged in a range of electronic symbol-making activities

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

containing conceptual processes, knowledge, and literacy strategies while using classroom computers that are equipped with multimedia word processing software. According to the National Center to Improve Practice (NCIP; 1998), providing learners with these computerized storybook reading opportunities—particularly those incorporating recently improved technologies in voice, sound graphics, and memory capacity—plays a crucial role in developing their reading skills. The attention given to research into the role of technology in literacy education was not restricted to finding out the relationship between computers and learner's reading progress but also addressed the impact of computers on developing children's writing skills. Computer technology contributes to developing children's early writing through improving their ability to use a word processor, organize their thoughts, and make several drafts of their writing.

In light of the above discussion, it can be concluded that a teacher plays a major role in providing learners with computer experience—or in excluding this tool from their classroom environment. Teachers are more likely to put their beliefs into actual instructional practice, because the current study has confirmed the congruence between the teachers' beliefs and their perceptions of their instructional practices in teaching reading and writing. In addition, teachers using technology in teaching reading and writing in their EFL classes were found to hold stronger beliefs and practices regarding the use of computer technology and are more likely to practice accordingly.

All of these mentioned presentation software for teaching have their respective unique qualities, and teachers can even amalgamate multiple software to make their demonstrations or presentations more effective.

The top three reasons why students liked using Prezi over PowerPoint was that it was fun, easy to use and its allowance for students to be more creative. From the students' point of view, their preference for their teachers to use Prezi was that it was 'fascinating' to see, helped them understand the subject matter and the fun and interesting way for them to learn. However, these reasons relied heavily on the quality of presentations by the teachers and the students. Similarly applying to information that flows well from one part to the next so that the students will be able to follow. Most students in this study agreed that they learnt more when creating their own Prezi. Consequently, the students with better presentation skills will be able to convey information more efficiently to other students and the quality of their presentations will also be paramount in increasing the students' understanding of the historical content.

Based on the findings that the students' motivation in learning history through the use of Prezi in class, this present study implies that promoting teachers to use Prezi in their teaching could lead to an improvement of students' performance in history examinations. Therefore, to improve the students' historical knowledge and overall interest in the subject of history, the teachers' motivation to use Prezi should be stimulated. To stimulate the teachers' motivation to use Prezi, it is essential to remove the cost barrier to use Prezi offline. Access to fast Internet at school, at home together with the cost of using Prezi are of great importance because these are the most influential factors that decide the success or failure of the approach.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4**

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The Effectiveness of Using an
Online Presentation Platform
in the Teaching and Learning of History

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Abstract

Most research on the aspects of teaching focuses on the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge. However, more studies are yet to be explored on the impact and efficiency of using technology as a tool for learning, particularly in the secondary history education. This study investigated how the online presentation platform called Prezi can be used effectively as a teaching and learning tool for the history subject. To test its effectiveness, students w

The use of software presentations during educational activities in schools and universities has become common due to many positive aspects. The key positive advantages of using software presentations during lessons in schools and during lectures at universities include a convenient way to present specific issues arranged in a specific chronological order, cause-and-effect sequence or other formula for dividing specific, presented issues into individual slides. The large scale of using software presentations during educational classes results from the use of a simple formula for editing individual slides and compatibility with other Ms Office system applications, as well as the possibility of pasting various types of graphic files and other materials that complement the typed text. The use of software presentations during educational activities includes the key attributes of using ICT in education.

During the presentation, the programs have a variety of advantages to the presenter and listeners. To progress through a slide show, the presenter just need to click a button, which allows the presenter to maintain eye contact with your audience and use your hands for emphasis. A software presentation often has a nice appearance and interesting graphics, which keeps the audience interested. Moreover, it can be projected on a big screen for a large auditorium or classroom. The disadvantage associated with software presentations is the need for certain requirements. A computer, projector, screen and electric power will be needed. You also need to dim the lights in the room to allow adequate visualization. The other disadvantage is the risk of technical problems. The success of the presentation depends entirely on the proper functioning of the technology.

After the presentation, the slides can be easily distributed to the necessary people for future reference. Unlike paperwork, a software presentation can be easily stored on the computer making it difficult to be lost or misplaced. The disadvantage is that the electronic file may be lost as a result of a computer virus or accidentally being deleted

Finally, I hope that software presentations will help to teachers make their lessons more effective and enjoyable for students.

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